

Diffusion and Activity Coefficient of Aqueous Cesium Chloride at 45°

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Diffusional studies with aqueous cesium chloride were carried out in the concentration range 0.04–1 M at 45° with the modified diaphragm cell technique. The results were analysed in the light of the theory of Onsager–Fuoss. From the data the activity coefficients in dilute solutions were computed. The results were also discussed with other univalent salts of cesium.

OUR earlier researches were devoted to the design and fabrication of a diaphragm cell apparatus¹ with a new drive system² and to the determination by it of diffusion coefficients of various valence order³, the computation of hydration number⁴ and activity coefficient^{4–6} at different temperatures.

We have now extended these studies to the determination of diffusion coefficient of cesium chloride at 45° and the results discussed in the light of the theory of Onsager–Fuoss⁷. Another objective of this work is to compute activity coefficient by the method suggested by Harned⁸ who had determined activity coefficient from diffusion coefficient obtained by conductometric technique. In the present work, diffusion coefficient has been obtained by the diaphragm cell technique^{1,2} and activity coefficient determined by the method of Harned⁸. The effect of temperature on these has also been investigated in the present investigation.

Experimental

The present work was carried out by a modified diaphragm cell in which a new drive system was introduced in this laboratory^{2,10}.

Cesium chloride and mercury used were of AnalaR grade. The pre-diffusion time (t_g) required to establish a steady state in the porous disc was estimated from the equation¹¹,

$$t_g = \frac{1.2 l^2}{D} \quad (1)$$

where, \bar{D} is the integral diffusion coefficient and l is the effective length of the diaphragm. It has recently been shown that Gordon's equation gives a t_g value which is considerably longer than that necessary to attain steady state¹¹. Experimental procedures for calibration and diffusion runs were the same as described elsewhere^{2,3}. An air-thermostat was set at 45° ($\pm 0.1^\circ$) by using toluene regulators and electronic relays.

Analysis of the solutions: The initial and final concentrations of the solution from a diffusion experiment were determined conductometrically. From the final conductance readings of the solution in the two compartments, when the steady state had been attained, the concentrations were read from the standard curves which were initially prepared by plotting conductance against concentration at $45 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The conductometer (Yellow Spring Inst. Co., U.S.A., model 31) was calibrated before use. The volume of the liquid in the pores of the diaphragm was determined as suggested earlier².

The cell constant (β) was calculated from the diaphragm cell equation⁹,

$$\beta = \frac{1}{Dt} \ln \frac{\Delta C^0}{\Delta C^t} \quad (2)$$

where the symbols have their usual meaning.

Diffusion runs with cesium chloride solutions: From the known time (t) and the initial and final concentrations, the integral diffusion coefficients (\bar{D}) were calculated by means of equation (2). The integral values were next converted into differential diffusion coefficients (D) by means of a short series of approximations¹² and employing equation (3),

$$D = \frac{\bar{D}^0}{C^0} + \frac{\sqrt{C^0}}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{d \bar{D}^0}{d \sqrt{C^0}} \right) \quad (3)$$

The integral and differential diffusion coefficients are given in Table 1.

Theory:

The theory of Onsager–Fuoss⁷ leads to the equation,

$$D = 1000RT (\nu_1 + \nu_2) \left(\frac{\bar{m}}{C} \right) \left(1 + C \frac{\partial \ln \gamma_{\pm}}{\partial C} \right) \quad (4)$$

where, ν_1 and ν_2 are the number of ions that dissociate in the solutions and \bar{m} is a function given by

$$\bar{m} = 1.0741 \times 10^{-20} \frac{\lambda_1^0, \lambda_2^0}{\nu_1 |Z_1|} + \Delta \bar{m}' + \Delta \bar{m}'' \quad (5)$$

TABLE 1—OBSERVED VALUES OF DIFFUSION COEFFICIENT OF CsCl AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS

Concn. mol dm ⁻³	× 10 ⁵ cm ² s ⁻¹		
	\bar{D}	D_{obs}	D_{calcd}
0.04	2.711 0	2.976 2	2.923 4
0.06	2.587 5	2.914 2	2.777 1
0.07	2.121 9	2.524 2	2.757 6
0.09	2 014 1	2.444 7	2.723 1
0.10	1.933 2	2.377 5	2.706 8
0.20	2.020 1	2.569 3	2.576 9
0.30	1.976 2	2.620 2	2.469 8
0.50	1.642 2	2 451 9	2.297 4
0.80	1.935 4	2.912 0	2.086 9
1.00	1.496 4	2.599 7	1.945 0

$D^{\circ} = 3.0767 \times 10^{-5}$ cm² s⁻¹ is the limiting value of diffusion coefficient.

where,

$$\Delta \bar{m}^{\pm} = - \frac{(|Z_2| \lambda_2^{\circ} - |Z_1| \lambda_1^{\circ})^2}{(\Lambda^{\circ})^2 |Z_1 Z_2| (v_1 + v_2)} \frac{3.132 \times 10^{-1} C \sqrt{\tau}}{\eta_0 (\epsilon T)^{1/2} (1 + ka)} \quad (6)$$

and

$$\Delta \bar{m}^{\pm} = \left(\frac{|Z_2| \lambda_1^{\circ} + |Z_1| \lambda_2^{\circ}}{\Lambda^{\circ}} \right)^2 \frac{9.304 \times 10^{-1} C^2 \phi ka}{\eta_0 (\epsilon T)^2} \quad (7)$$

the activity term $\left(1 + C \frac{\partial \ln y_{\pm}}{\partial C}\right)$ is represented by

$$\left(1 + C \frac{\partial \ln y_{\pm}}{\partial C}\right) = 1 - \frac{1.1514 S_{(1)} \sqrt{C}}{(1 + A' \sqrt{C})^2} + 2.303BC - C\psi(d) \quad (8)$$

In these equations, D is the diffusion coefficient in (cm² s⁻¹), T is the absolute temperature, C is the concentration (mol dm⁻³), y_{\pm} is the activity coefficient on the molar concentration scale, ϵ is the dielectric constant of the water and η_0 its viscosity. The ionic conductances of the cation and anion are λ_1° and λ_2° , and Λ° is the equivalent conductance at infinite dilution of the electrolyte. $S_{(1)}$ is the limiting slope of the Debye and Hückel theory, $A' \sqrt{C} = A \sqrt{\tau} = ka$ in which τ is the ionic concentration, k the reciprocal radius, a the mean distance of closest approach of the ions and $A' = 35.86 \times a (\epsilon T)^{-1/2}$. The quantity, $\phi(ka)$ is the exponential integral function of the theory which may be obtained from tables given by Harned and Owen¹³. B is an empirical constant, $C\psi(d)$, being the term required to convert the expression from the rational to molar activity coefficient and is given by

$$\psi(d) = \frac{(\partial d / \partial C) + 0.001 (vM_1 - M_2)}{d + 0.001C (vM_1 - M_2)} \quad (9)$$

where, d is the density, M_1 the molar mass of the solvent and M_2 that of the solute.

The limiting value of the diffusion coefficient was obtained from the equation discussed elsewhere¹³.

Results and Discussion

From the results recorded in Table 1 it can be seen that the observed values of diffusion coefficients in the concentration range 0.04–1.0 M are not in agreement with those calculated from the theory of Onsager–Fuoss⁷. There is a decrease in the D values from 2.9762×10^{-5} to 2.3775×10^{-5} cm² s⁻¹ as the concentration is raised from 0.04–0.1 M whereas there is a regular decrease in the theoretical values for the whole concentration range investigated. Except at 0.50 M where there is a decrease in the experimental value of diffusion coefficient, the results increase from 2.5693×10^{-5} to 2.9120×10^{-5} cm² s⁻¹ upto 0.80 M and finally again a decrease from 2.9120×10^{-5} to 2.5997×10^{-5} cm² s⁻¹ at 1.0 M is observed. The theoretical values computed involved both the first and second order electrophoretic corrections rather than only the first order effect and this is generally the trend when the O–F theory is employed for univalent⁸ and bivalent salts, exception being for higher valence type, i.e. 3 : 1 or 4 : 1 when it is considered not at all appropriate to use the second order electrophoretic correction in the theory. This aspect has already been studied and reported by Stokes¹⁴ and needs no further discussion here. The departure of the experimental results from those of the theory has been considered to be due to the effect of hydration, changing viscosity and changing dielectric constant of the medium. Since Cs^I ion has a hydration¹⁵ of 2.5 it is clear that the hydrated species must behave in a manner quite different from the one predicated by any theory based on the incomplete understanding of the hydration concept. The present departure of the observed values from those of O–F theory⁷ is, therefore, not unexpected.

Effect of temperature : From a glance at equation (4) it is clear that diffusion coefficient is a direct function of the temperature. Therefore, according to the O–F theory⁷ increase in temperature must increase the diffusion coefficient. The effect of temperature on diffusion coefficient was studied in this laboratory¹⁶ for Mg(NO₃)₂ and the above fact was found to be true. In the present case with CsCl at 45°, the results are compared with those obtained by conductometric technique⁹, at 25° and it can be concluded that the diffusion coefficient increases with temperature.

Activity coefficient : According to equation (4) on rearrangement,

$$\frac{D}{1000 \nu RT (m/c)} - 1 = D' = C \frac{\partial \ln y_{\pm}}{\partial C} \quad (10)$$

which defines the function⁸ D' . From this equation,

$$\log y_{\pm} = \frac{\ln y_{\pm}}{2.3026} = 0.8686 \int_0^C \frac{D'}{\sqrt{C}} d\sqrt{C} \quad (11)$$

$$\text{or } \lim_{C \rightarrow 0} \left[\frac{D'}{\sqrt{C}} = \frac{\partial \ln y_{\pm}}{2\partial \sqrt{C}} = - \frac{2.3026}{2} S_{(1)} \right] \quad (12)$$

TABLE 2—DATA EMPLOYED FOR THEORETICAL CALCULATIONS OF THE DIFFUSION COEFFICIENTS FOR CESIUM CHLORIDE

Concn.	$\phi(ka)$	\bar{m}/C $\times 10^{20}$	$\Delta\bar{m}'/C$ $\times 10^{20}$	$\Delta\bar{m}''/C$ $\times 10^{20}$	$1 + C \frac{\partial \ln \gamma_{\pm}}{\partial C}$	$-C\psi(a)$
0.04	0.659 4	58.910 6	0.000 16	0.790 95	0.905 9	0.014 5
0.06	0.516 7	59.049 1	0.000 19	0.929 47	0.888 9	0.021 6
0.07	0.473 7	59.113 8	0.000 20	0.994 23	0.881 7	0.025 1
0.09	0.412 5	59.232 8	0.000 21	1.083 28	0.869 0	0.032 1
0.10	0.385 4	59.275 1	0.000 22	1.113 26	0.863 2	0.035 5
0.20	0.250 7	59.622 8	0.000 23	1.155 54	0.816 9	0.068 5
0.30	0.181 7	59.754 2	0.000 29	1.503 34	0.781 3	0.099 3
0.50	0.125 6	60.002 3	0.000 33	1.634 67	0.723 7	0.155 1
0.80	0.083 7	60.128 2	0.000 39	1.882 93	0.656 1	0.226 7
1.00	0.068 7	60.179 2	0.000 44	2.008 86	0.610 9	0.268 0

where $S_{(t)}$ is the theoretical slope of the logarithm of the activity coefficient. By plotting $D' \sqrt{C}$ vs \sqrt{C} to this limiting value, the activity coefficient (γ_{\pm}) can be computed by equation (11) by graphical integration.

Table 1 contains the observed values of the diffusion coefficient of cesium chloride at the concentrations indicated. Due to the limitation of the diaphragm cell technique^{1,2} the diffusion coefficients were experimentally obtained at 0.04 M and above. Table 2 includes all the data necessary for computing the mobility term \bar{m}/C which is a combined effect due to first ($\Delta\bar{m}'$) and second ($\Delta\bar{m}''$) order electrophoretic corrections and these are also given in Table 2 for recording the contribution in the $D_{\text{calcd.}}$ values obtained by using equations (4-9). The values of D' and $-D' \sqrt{C}$ are recorded in Table 3.

From a plot of $D' \sqrt{C}$ vs \sqrt{C} the activity coefficients of CsCl at the dilute concentrations range 0.0001-0.0225 M can be computed since the limiting value of D'/\sqrt{C} is known and the deviation of the activity coefficient from unity can be measured by the entire area under the graph. Although it is clear that the value of the mean distance of approach of the ion (a) and which is needed for calculating the mobility term is arbitrary, yet the variation of \bar{m}/C with concentration is small and is not very sensitive to the value of a . The activity

TABLE 3—COMPUTATION OF D'/\sqrt{C} FOR DETERMINING THE ACTIVITY COEFFICIENT AND DENSITY OF CsCl AT 45°

Concn. \sqrt{C} mol dm ⁻³	$-D'$	$-D'/\sqrt{C}$	Concn. (C) mol dm ⁻³	Density g cm ⁻³
0.020 0	0.061 0	0.304 3	0.000 1	0.990 25
0.244 9	0.671 0	0.274 1	0.000 4	0.990 30
0.264 6	0.192 9	0.723 8	0.000 9	0.990 42
0.300 0	0.219 9	0.723 8	0.001 6	0.990 55
0.316 2	0.241 8	0.764 8	0.002 5	0.990 80
0.447 2	0.185 6	0.414 9	0.003 6	0.991 10
0.547 7	0.171 1	0.312 5	0.004 9	0.991 45
0.707 1	0.227 6	0.321 9	0.006 4	0.991 70
0.894 4	0.084 6	0.094 5	0.008 1	0.992 20
1.000 0	0.183 4	0.183 4	0.010 0	0.992 70
			0.012 1	0.993 05
			0.014 4	0.993 75
			0.016 9	0.994 40
			0.016 9	0.995 10
			0.019 6	0.995 10
			0.022 5	0.995 75
			0.100 0	1.015 25

coefficients in the above mentioned concentration range are recorded in Table 4.

In order to compare the computed values of activity coefficients with the theoretical in the above concentration range the theory of Guggenheim¹⁷ was employed. According to this theory the activity coefficient (f_{\pm}) can be obtained from equation (13),

$$\log f_{\pm} = -\frac{S_w \sqrt{C}}{1 + \sqrt{C}} \quad (13)$$

TABLE 4—ACTIVITY COEFFICIENT OF CsCl IN DILUTE AQUEOUS SOLUTION AT 45°

Concn. mol dm ⁻³	0.000 1	0.000 4	0.000 9	0.001 6	0.002 5	0.003 6	0.004 9	0.006 4	0.008 1	0.010 0	0.012 1	0.014 4	0.016 9	0.019 6	0.022 5
γ_{\pm} (obs.)	0.977 2	0.957 9	0.938 0	0.918 7	0.899 9	0.881 4	0.864 2	0.847 0	0.830 8	0.814 5	0.798 9	0.783 8	0.769 1	0.755 3	0.741 3
γ_{\pm} (calcd.)	0.988 1	0.976 3	0.965 0	0.954 0	0.943 4	0.932 9	0.922 9	0.913 1	0.903 4	0.894 2	0.885 0	0.876 2	0.867 5	0.859 0	0.850 7
f_{\pm} (Rational activity coeff.) (calcd.)	0.988 1	0.976 3	0.965 1	0.954 1	0.943 6	0.933 3	0.923 4	0.913 7	0.904 2	0.895 2	0.886 1	0.877 6	0.869 2	0.861 0	0.852 9

TABLE 5—SPECIFIC DATA EMPLOYED FOR THEORETICAL CALCULATIONS*

$\lambda_2^0 = 107.53$	$\nu_1 = 1$	$\eta_0 = 5.96 \times 10^{-3}$
$\lambda_2^0 = 108.92$	$\nu_2 = 1$	$S_{(1)} = 0.5295$
$\epsilon = 71.70$	$Z_1 = 1$	$M_1 = 18$
$T = 318.16$	$Z_2 = 1$	$M_2 = 168.96$

*For definitions and units see the text.

where, $S_{(1)}$ is the theoretical slope recorded in Table 3, and f_{\pm} is the rational activity coefficient. To convert these into the molar scale use is made of equation¹⁸ (14),

$$y_{\pm} = f_{\pm} \frac{d_0}{d + 0.001 C (\nu W_A - W_B)} \quad (14)$$

where, d_0 = density of water at 45°, d = density of solution, W_A = molecular weight of water and W_B = molecular weight of CsCl. The densities of CsCl at 45° were obtained by pycnometer and these are recorded in Table 3. The values of f_{\pm} as well as y_{\pm} are presented in Table 4. A glance at Table 4 clearly indicates that there is a fair agreement between the observed and calculated values of activity coefficients from 0.0001–0.0036 M but more pronounced departures are noted above this concentration when the percentage agreement with the theory falls from 95 to 87% at 0.0225 M . Similar procedures were previously also adopted for finding only the observed activity coefficient in the concentration range¹⁹ 0.0025–0.2500 M for CsBr. The values of y_{\pm} at 0.0025, 0.01 and 0.0225 M for this salt at 45° were 0.9097, 0.8303 and 0.7598 and 0.8999, 0.8145 and 0.7413 for CsCl. The values at other concentrations can not be compared due to the difference in the concentrations of CsBr studied as compared to those of CsCl investigated in the present study.

Guggenheim¹⁷ in order to incorporate the effect of ion-pair formation²⁰, ion size, lowering of dielectric constant (Hückel), polarisability etc. introduced¹⁷ the term λC in equation (13) and the f_{\pm} is then given as

$$\log f_{\pm} = -\frac{S_{(1)} \sqrt{C}}{1 + \sqrt{C}} + \lambda C \quad (15)$$

The values of λ for various uni-univalent salts for f_{\pm} at 0.1 M concentrations are given elsewhere²¹. The values of activity coefficients for all these salts are obtained at 25° and no value of λ is given at 45°. For CsNO₃, $\lambda = 0$ indicates no contribution due to ion-pair formation, ion size and polarisability etc. But in our case with CsCl at 45°, this value of λ computed is -1.126. The value of y_{\pm}

obtained graphically is, however, 0.5689 at 0.1 M and f_{\pm} comes out to be 0.5757 (density $d_{0.1M} = 1.0153$). Negative values of λ at 25° are also obtained for KClO₃ (-0.143), KNO₃ (-0.296), NaIO₃ (-0.35) and KIO₃ (-0.35). One point needs mentioning here is that the values of λ if obtained at different temperatures will definitely give us deeper understanding of the type of ionic interaction discussed above.

The activity coefficients at 25° for CsCl and at 45° for CsBr were also determined at varying concentrations and these are recorded elsewhere^{22, 23}. It is clear that the y_{\pm} decreases with the rise in concentration for both these salts. Similar behaviour is observed in the present case with CsCl at 45°.

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